

On Anacardic Acid. Part I. Anacardic Acid and Tetrahydroanacardic Acid.

BY P. PARAMESWARAN PILLAY.

Anacardic acid forms about 90% of the corrosive oil of the pericarp of the nut of *Anacardium occidentale*, Linn. This tree (Hindi, *Kaju*; English, *cashewnut*) is an evergreen, 19-20 feet high, growing in the hotter parts of India, especially near the sea. Medically, the tarry oil is useful for leprosy, ringworm and obstinate ulcers. It is exported in large quantities from the west coast for use as a raw material in the preparation of synthetic resins and varnishes. Anacardic acid was first separated from the crude oil of the pericarp by Stadelers (*Annalen*, 1847, **63**, 137) by precipitation of the acid from an alcoholic solution of the oil with freshly precipitated lead hydroxide, and decomposing the insoluble lead salt with ammonium sulphide, followed by the liberation of the oil from the ammonium soap by dilute sulphuric acid. Stadelers prepared several metallic derivatives and as the result of many analyses gave it the formula $C_{44}H_{32}O_7$. Ruhemann and Skinner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1887, **51**, 663; *Ber.*, 1887, **20**, 1861) repeated his work and established the formula $C_{22}H_{32}O_3$ for the acid. They also prepared a methyl ester and suggested that it was probably a hydroxycarboxylic acid.

In the course of the present investigation it was observed that by Stadelers's method of preparation (*loc. cit.*), aqueous solution of the ammonium salt of anacardic acid was so thick and viscous that it was very difficult to filter it from the fine suspension of lead sulphide. An alternative method was, therefore, devised, based on the solubility of the lead salt in ether. This method has been found to be very much quicker and easier, although the product is a little more coloured.

Careful analyses, estimation of silver in the silver salt and molecular weight determinations support the formula $C_{22}H_{32}O_3$ of Ruhemann and Skinner (*loc. cit.*) The Zerewitneoff method revealed the presence of 2 active hydrogen in the molecule of the acid. Attempts to methylate it by methyl sulphate and alkali or

to acetylate it by boiling with acetic anhydride were unsuccessful. A unique property of anacardic acid must be noted, viz., that when an alcoholic solution of silver nitrate is added to the acid, the silver salt is precipitated immediately as a white powder accompanied by the simultaneous liberation of nitric acid.

Anacardic acid in very dilute alkaline solution is oxidised with extreme ease by potassium permanganate and from the oxidation products oxalic acid and oenanthic acids were isolated and indications of the presence of other dicarboxylic acids were also obtained. No cyclic carboxylic acid could be isolated. Again, when oxidised with concentrated nitric acid on the boiling water-bath, a good quantity of oxalic acid was obtained, but here also no nitrocarboxylic acid could be isolated.

The degree of unsaturation of anacardic acid was estimated by titration against bromine in cooled chloroform solution, and showed that it contained two aliphatic double bonds. The acid was hydrogenated in alcoholic solution in the presence of palladised charcoal as catalyst to give a tetrahydroanacardic acid. Derivatives of tetrahydroanacardic acid have been prepared and studied (*vide* experimental).

The material used was obtained from the Malabar coast.

EXPERIMENTAL.

An improved method for the preparation of anacardic acid.—An alcoholic solution of the crude extract was shaken with an excess of freshly precipitated lead hydroxide. The lead precipitate was filtered, washed with alcohol and shaken in an inert atmosphere with ether which dissolved lead anacardate. It was decanted off and repeatedly shaken in an inert atmosphere with dilute hydrochloric acid, then with water, dried and the solvent distilled off. The anacardic acid remained behind as a brown oil. Either benzene or petroleum ether can replace ether but they tend to form emulsions. This method is very suitable for the preparation of large quantities of the acid. For purifying the acid, it was dissolved in alcohol, neutralised with a slight excess of aqueous ammonia, then aqueous barium chloride solution added till there was a slight cloudiness. The solution was then shaken with some powdered wood charcoal and kept aside. Anacardic acid came down on acidification and dilution as a light brown oil and constitutes nearly 90% of the extract.

The homogeneity of the acid.—The acid, thus obtained, was fractionated by means of alcoholic basic lead acetate into four fractions and

the acid recovered from each of these fractions. The two middle fractions had m. p. between 22-25° and the two others solidified indefinitely some degrees lower. On catalytic reduction of each of these fractions the tetrahydroanacardic acid was obtained in nearly quantitative yield, the m. p. ranging from 86-92°. Even the low-melting product, when twice crystallised gave the substance melting at 93° in good yield.

Properties of anacardic acid.—A pure sample of anacardic acid has the following properties: m.p. 23-25°; $d_{20}^{20} = 1.0002$; $n_D^{20} = 1.5163$. It is a light brown viscous oil soluble in all common organic solvents. [Found: C, 76.6; 76.8; H, 9.5, 9.5; M.W. (in acetone), 367, 358. $C_{22}H_{32}O_3$ requires C, 76.7; H, 9.5 per cent. M.W., 344]. It is soluble in dilute ammonia and in *N/10*-NaOH but with higher concentrations of NaOH it gives a white sodium derivative insoluble in water but soluble in alcohol. The silver salt was prepared by adding alcoholic silver nitrate to an alcoholic solution of anacardic acid, washed and dried in *vacuo*. (Found: Ag, 23.68, 23.72. $C_{22}H_{31}O_3Ag$ requires Ag, 23.94 per cent). The number of active hydrogen by the Zerewitenoff method was found to be two. (Found: Active H, 0.65; 2 H requires 0.58 per cent.) The acid gave an intense violet colouration with alcoholic $FeCl_3$, a slight shade bluer than that given by salicylic acid and of the exact tint as that of *o*-cresotic acid.

Esterification and acetylation by the ordinary methods proved unsuccessful, but the silver salt treated in dry ether with ethyl iodide gave an oil which was insoluble in ammonia and which could not be distilled in *vacuo* without decomposition.

Oxidation of anacardic acid with potassium permanganate.—The acid (10 g.) was dissolved in dilute ammonia and the solution diluted with water to 300 c.c. and oxidised by the slow addition of well powdered potassium permanganate (37 g.) with vigorous stirring. The decolourisation was very quick. The product when filtered, acidified and extracted with ether gave 4.8 g. of acids. From the manganese dioxide precipitate by dissolving in sulphurous acid 3.3 g. of acids were obtained. This was further dissolved in dilute ammonia and oxidised with potassium permanganate (12 g.). From the aqueous filtrates collected together, by neutralisation and precipitation with calcium chloride nearly 2g. of calcium oxalate were obtained. From the other acids, by treatment with petroleum ether 1.8 g. of a liquid acid, soluble in this solvent, were obtained which when distilled boiled chiefly between 220-225°. [Found: C, 64.3; H, 10.3; Ag (in Ag salt), 45.1

per cent. $C_7H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 64.6; H, 10.8; Ag (in Ag salt), 45.6 per cent]. It was confirmed as oenanthic acid by preparing the anilide melting at 67°.

The acids insoluble in petrol were fractionated through the calcium salt. One fraction was obtained as solid, m. p. 150°. It could not be obtained crystalline but appeared to behave like a fatty dicarboxylic acid. No ring acid could be isolated.

Oxidation with concentrated nitric acid.—Anacardic acid (10 g.) was treated in small lots with concentrated nitric acid (*d* 1.48, 75 c.c.) so that the vigorous reaction could be checked, and the product twice evaporated down on the water-bath with nitric acid. The residue when washed with 15 c.c. of hot water gave a yellow solution which when evaporated gave oxalic acid (2.7 g.). The liquid acids insoluble in water were not examined in detail as they did not give indications of the presence of a nitro-acid containing phenolic hydroxyl.

Titration of anacardic acid against bromine.—The acid (1.53 g.) in ice-cooled chloroform solution, titrated against bromine in the same solvent took up 1.40 g. of bromine (2 double bonds require 1.42 g.). The course of the addition was followed by means of potassium iodide-starch paper. The tetrabromide was insoluble in petrol and was obtained as a semi-solid, but could not be obtained in a crystalline form.

Catalytic hydrogenation of anacardic acid.—The acid (4 g.) in 50 c.c. of alcohol was added to palladised charcoal which was previously suspended in 50 c.c. of alcohol and shaken in a hydrogen atmosphere till it had ceased to absorb any more hydrogen (522 c.c. at N.T.P. 2 H_2 require 517 c.c. at N. T. P.). It was filtered, water was added and the solution cooled, when the product was precipitated as a white crystalline mass, m.p. 88-90°, yield 4.0 g. It was crystallised once from alcohol and then from benzene and petroleum ether in shining silky needles, m.p. 92.5-93°. The tetrahydroanacardic acid is soluble in the common organic solvents except in glacial acetic acid and petroleum ether and its chemical properties are quite similar to that of anacardic acid. (Found: C, 75.6, 75.8; H, 10.5, 10.4. $C_{22}H_{36}O_3$ requires C, 75.9; H, 10.4 per cent). The number of active hydrogen found by Zerewitenoff method was 2 (Found: H, 0.52; 2H requires 0.57 per cent). A solution of the acid in absolute alcohol was saturated with hydrochloric acid gas when a substance crystallised out in needles, which was found to be not the ester but the original substance. In order to obtain the ester, the acid was converted to the silver salt through the

ammonium salt. (Found: Ag, 23·57, 23·61. $C_{22}H_{35}O_3Ag$ requires Ag, 23·72 per cent).

Methyl tetrahydroanacardate.—The silver salt suspended in dry ether was kept aside for 3 days with excess of methyl iodide. It was filtered, the ether evaporated off and crystallised by cooling an alcoholic solution in ice. It was pressed on a porous plate and recrystallised in flat needles, insoluble in ammonia, m.p. 49°. (Found: C, 76·4; H, 10·4. $C_{23}H_{38}O_3$ requires C, 76·3; H, 10·5 per cent).

Ethyl tetrahydroanacardate was obtained in a similar manner with ethyl iodide as silky needles, m.p. 38°. (Found: C, 76·7; H, 10·5. $C_{24}H_{40}O_3$ requires C, 76·6; H, 10·6 per cent).

As regards the phenolic hydroxyl group of tetrahydroanacardic acid it was found that it resisted the ordinary methods of acetylation, benzoylation and methoxylation.

The acetyl derivative.—The acid (0·5g.) was dissolved in dry pyridine, (3 c.c.), cooled in ice and acetyl chloride (0·3 c.c.) was very cautiously added with shaking. After 10 minutes the mixture was carefully warmed on the water-bath to a clear solution, cooled and diluted with water. The precipitated oil was washed well with water, purified through the ammonium salt, cooled, acidified and the acid obtained was crystallised from alcohol as needles, m.p. 78° which do not give any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 74·0; H, 9·6. $C_{24}H_{38}O_4$ requires C, 73·8; H, 9·7 per cent).

Monobromotetrahydroanacardic acid.—To the tetrahydroanacardic acid (0·5 g.) dissolved in carbon disulphide (5 c.c.) bromine (0·23 g.) was added dissolved in 3 c.c. of the solvent. The mixture was occasionally slightly warmed. There was evolution of HBr and decolourisation of the solution which was evaporated down and the solid crystallised from benzene, m.p., 77°. (Found: Br, 18·3. $C_{22}H_{35}O_3Br$ requires Br, 18·7 per cent).

Oxidation of tetrahydroanacardic acid: Isolation of oxalic acid and palmitic acid.—To tetrahydroanacardic acid (4 g.) dissolved in acetone (300 c.c.) and water (60 c.c.) was added a solution of potassium permanganate (12·5 g.) in acetone (300 c.c.) and water (100 c.c.). The oxidation was completed by warming on the water-bath for 1 hour. The mixture was cooled, filtered, the manganese dioxide precipitate was washed first with a little acetone, then with boiling water, and the acetone distilled off. The aqueous residue was cooled and acidified. It gave an effervescence of carbon dioxide and 1·7 g. of a fatty acid were obtained which melted at 50-53°; recrystallised from

alcohol it melted at 53-55°. It was distilled under reduced pressure and the distillate crystallised thrice from alcohol, when colourless needles were obtained (0.6 g.), m.p. 60-61°; there being no depression on admixture with a sample of pure palmitic acid. (Found: C, 74.9; H, 12.7. $C_{16}H_{32}O_2$ requires C, 75.0; H, 12.5 per cent). The aqueous filtrate showed the presence of oxalic acid.

PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
MADRAS.

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On Anacardic Acid. Part II. The Constitution of Tetrahydroanacardic Acid.

BY P. PARAMESWARAN PILLAY.

Another line of investigation which threw more light on the constitution of anacardic acid was based on its behaviour on heating. On heating the acid in an atmosphere of nitrogen to 230° and distilling the product, there was obtained besides undistillable resin, an oil boiling at 215.20°/14mm. in an yield of approximately 25%. The same product was obtained in an yield of 50% when anacardic acid was distilled in *vacuo*. This oil, which is referred to as anacardol, was found by its analysis, behaviour and catalytic reduction to be the simple decarboxylated product of anacardic acid, standing in the same relationship to it as phenol to salicylic acid. It was observed that, once the carboxyl group became eliminated from anacardic acid, the hydroxyl group became easily reactive, but here again it was found to be more advantageous to study it in the saturated product.

Titration against bromine revealed the presence of two double bonds and on catalytic reduction four atoms of hydrogen were quickly taken up (*cf.* Part I) and the same compound was obtained in good yield, when tetrahydroanacardic acid was distilled under reduced pressure. It was found, however, that if tetrahydroanacardic acid is first decarboxylated by prolonged heating at 200-220° at ordinary pressure it gives besides tetrahydroanacardol, about 26% of another product as needles, almost insoluble in alcohol and melting at 49°.